

Milestone: M3.2: First version of Software Management Plan interface implemented in Data Stewardship Wizard

Lead Participant: UOCHB

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Due: 31 January 2025 (12)

Date Of Completion: 20/01/2025

Means of Verification

- report ([document](#))
- content in [DSW Registry](#)
- content in [Software Management Wizard](#)

Milestone Delayed (if yes, please explain)

no

Project participants & others

- UOCHB: Marek Suchánek, Jan Slifka
- SIB: Vassilios Ioannidis
- UU: Matthias Nyberg
- SDU: Veit Schwämmle
- T3.2 members (see report document)

Next action steps

- plan topic-specific workshops to improve SMPs
- gather user feedback on the first version and incorporate it in next version(s) of the content
- develop integrations and other features based on the collected feedback and improvements

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